

The complexity of class L

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A major complexity classes are L , $POLYLOGTIME$ and $\oplus L$. A logarithmic Turing machine has a read-only input tape, a write-only output tape, and some read/write work tapes. The work tapes may contain $O(\log n)$ symbols. L is the complexity class containing those decision problems that can be decided by a deterministic logarithmic Turing machine. We define the complexity class $POLYLOGTIME$ as the problems which can be decided by a random access machine in poly-logarithmic time. We prove there is problem in the complexity class L which cannot be solved by a random access machine in poly-logarithmic time. Hence, we show $L \not\subseteq POLYLOGTIME$. The complexity class $\oplus L$ has the same relation to L as $\oplus P$ does to P . We demonstrate there is a complete problem for $\oplus L$ that can be logarithmic space reduced to a problem in L . Consequently, we show $L = \oplus L$.

CCS Concepts: • **Theory of computation** → **Complexity classes**; *Problems, reductions and completeness*;

Additional Key Words and Phrases: Complexity classes, Logarithmic space, Maximum, XOR-3SAT, Clique

1 OBJECTIVES

We prove the complexity class L is not contained into the another class $POLYLOGTIME$. Moreover, we demonstrate the complexity class L is equal to the another class $\oplus L$.

2 METHODS

The lower bound in finding a maximum into a collection with n positive integers is within $n - 1$ comparisons [3]. When the size of the input is polynomially bounded by n , then there are variants of this problem which cannot be solved by a random access machine in poly-logarithmic time. In addition, we use the logarithmic space reduction to prove when some complexity class is contained in L : We show that some complete problem of the class can be logarithmic space reduced to another language in L because L is closed under logarithmic space reductions [5].

3 FINDINGS

On the one hand, we show a problem $LOG-MAXIMUM$ that should be solved with no less than n comparisons. The value n is exponential in relation to the logarithmic size of the instances of $LOG-MAXIMUM$. Consequently, this cannot be solved by a random access machine in poly-logarithmic time. However, $LOG-MAXIMUM$ can be solved in logarithmic space.

On the other hand, we show a problem $MONOTONE-XOR-4SAT$ that is complete for $\oplus L$. Moreover, we prove this language can be logarithmic space reduced to another problem in L . Consequently, there is a complete problem for $\oplus L$ which is in L as well. In this way, the complexity class L is equal to $\oplus L$.

This proof solves some of the problems which remained open from several decades such as L versus $POLYLOGTIME$ and L versus $\oplus L$. Whether $L = P$ is another fundamental question that it is as important as it is unresolved [5]. All efforts to solve the L versus P problem have failed [5]. We hope these results might help us to solve this interesting problem in the near future.

4 APPLICATION

Now, we can solve in logarithmic space some complete problems in $\oplus L$ such as the solving of a linear system over Z_2 [4].

5 RESULTS

5.1 L versus $POLYLOGTIME$

How many comparisons are necessary to determine the maximum of a collection of n elements? We can easily obtain an upper bound of $n - 1$ comparisons: examine each element of the set in turn and keep track of the biggest element seen so far [3]. In the following procedure, we assume that the collection resides in an array A , where $length[A] = n$ [3].

Algorithm 1 *MAXIMUM's Polynomial Time algorithm*

```
1: procedure MAXIMUM( $A$ )
2:   /*Assign the first element*/
3:    $max \leftarrow A[1]$ 
4:   /*Iterate for the elements of the array*/
5:   for  $i \leftarrow 2$  to  $n$  do
6:     /*When the element  $A[i]$  is greater than  $max$ */
7:     if  $max < A[i]$  then
8:       /*Update the new value of  $max$ */
9:        $max \leftarrow A[i]$ 
10:    end if
11:  end for
12:  return  $max$ 
13: end procedure
```

Is this the best we can do? Yes, since we can obtain a lower bound of $n - 1$ comparisons for the problem of determining the maximum [3].

Definition 5.1. LOG-MAXIMUM

INSTANCE: A natural number n , a positive integer x represented as a binary string of bit-length $\lceil \log n \rceil$ and an array A of n positive integers not necessarily distinct such that if $y = A[i]$ for some $1 \leq i \leq n$, then y is represented as a binary string of bit-length $\lceil \log n \rceil$. For example, for $x = 3$ and $n = 32$, then x is represented as a binary string of bit-length $5 = \lceil \log n \rceil$ as follows 00011: Note that the bit-length of 00011 is equal to 5.

QUESTION: Is x the maximum number in A ?

Definition 5.2. We define $|\dots|$ as the function that counts the number of bits of any binary string. Note if there is a comma separator or a blank symbol that separates some binary strings, then these symbols are not taking into account in the function $|\dots|$.

THEOREM 5.3. $LOG-MAXIMUM \notin POLYLOGTIME$.

PROOF. We need to compare the bit-length of the binary string representation of x and the elements of A with $\lceil \log n \rceil$. The total amount is $n + 1$ comparisons. In general, the number of comparisons that should do every algorithm which decides the language $LOG-MAXIMUM$ is greater than $n - 1$ even though there could exist a possibility where the verification of the bit-length binary representation might be avoided. The reason is because we need to check that x is the maximum in the array A of n positive integers.

Indeed, how many comparisons are necessary to determine whether a positive integer x is the maximum of an array of n positive integers? We can easily obtain an upper bound of n comparisons: examine each element of the array in turn and keep track of the biggest element seen so far and

Algorithm 2 *LOG-MAXIMUM's Polynomial Time algorithm*

```
1: procedure LOG-MAXIMUM( $n, x, A$ )
2:   /*Compare the bit-length of  $x$  with  $\lceil \log n \rceil$ */
3:   if  $|x| \neq \lceil \log n \rceil$  then
4:     /*Reject*/
5:     return "no"
6:   end if
7:   /*Iterate for the elements of the array*/
8:   for  $i \leftarrow 1$  to  $n$  do
9:     /*When the element  $A[i]$  bit-length is different of  $\lceil \log n \rceil$ */
10:    if  $|A[i]| \neq \lceil \log n \rceil$  then
11:      /*Reject*/
12:      return "no"
13:    end if
14:  end for
15:  /*Assign the maximum element of  $A$ */
16:   $max \leftarrow \text{MAXIMUM}(A)$ 
17:  /*If the number  $x$  is equal to the maximum of the array*/
18:  if  $max = x$  then
19:    /*Accept*/
20:    return "yes"
21:  else
22:    /*Otherwise reject*/
23:    return "no"
24:  end if
25: end procedure
```

finally, we compare the ultimate result with x . In the following procedure, we describe a simple algorithm that uses the previous Algorithm 1.

We can obtain a lower bound of $n - 1$ comparisons for the problem of determining the maximum and one another comparison to check whether this is equal to x [3]. Is this the best amount of comparisons we can do? Yes, think of any algorithm that determines the maximum as a tournament among the elements [3]. Each comparison is a match in the tournament in which the bigger of the two elements wins [3]. The key observation is that every element except the winner must lose at least one match [3]. Finally, we compare the winner with x [3]. Hence, n comparisons are necessary to determine whether x is the maximum of the array of positive integers, and the algorithm *LOG-MAXIMUM* is optimal with respect to the number of comparisons performed to find the maximum [3]. Consequently, *LOG-MAXIMUM* cannot be decided in less than n steps, where n is the natural number of the input. Actually, if we sum the total amount of comparisons in the Algorithm 2, then this is equal to $2 \times n + 1$.

If the instance (n, x, A) belongs to *LOG-MAXIMUM*, then the bit-length of the binary representation of (n, x, A) is polynomially bounded by $\lceil \log n \rceil \times (n + 2)$ since $|n| \leq \lceil \log n \rceil$, $|x| = \lceil \log n \rceil$ and $|A| = \lceil \log n \rceil \times n$ because the array A contains n elements represented by binary strings of bit-length $\lceil \log n \rceil$. As we see above, we should use no less than n comparisons to know whether the instance (n, x, A) is an element of *LOG-MAXIMUM*. Hence, we cannot always accept every instance (n, x, A) of *LOG-MAXIMUM* in time $O(\log^k |n, x, A|)$ by a random access machine for some fixed

constant $k > 0$ that we could choose. The reason is because there is not a fixed constant $k > 0$ such that $\log^k |n, x, A| \geq n$ for every value of n , where n is the natural number of the input. Certainly, $|n, x, A| \leq \lceil \log n \rceil \times (n + 2)$, and thus $\log |n, x, A| \leq \log(\lceil \log n \rceil \times (n + 2)) \leq 4 \times \lceil \log n \rceil$. However, n is exponentially greater than $4 \times \lceil \log n \rceil$, therefore there is not a fixed constant $k > 0$ such that $(4 \times \lceil \log n \rceil)^k \geq n$ for every value of the natural number n . \square

THEOREM 5.4. $LOG\text{-}MAXIMUM \in L$.

PROOF. Given a selected instance of the language $LOG\text{-}MAXIMUM$, we are going to demonstrate we can decide it in logarithmic space. In the following Algorithm 3, we assume the function $|\dots|$ calculates the bit-length of a binary string in logarithmic space.

Is this a logarithmic space algorithm? Yes, since we compare the value of the functions $|x|$ and $|A[i]|$ (the i^{th} element of A) using a logarithmic space. Indeed, the calculated bit-length of x and $A[i]$ only uses at most logarithmic space. Certainly, in the comparison from the bit-length of $A[i]$ and x with $\lceil \log n \rceil$ we halt and reject immediately when $|A[i]|$ or $|x|$ exceeds $\lceil \log n \rceil$ at least in one digit and thus, we do not need to calculate completely the values of $|A[i]|$ or $|x|$ to reject. In this way, we just keep at most logarithmic space in the calculation of $|A[i]|$ and $|x|$. Finally, since both bit-lengths are equal, then we compare the elements $A[i]$ and x bit by bit. For this purpose, we compare only two bits in the input tape over the same position j from x and $A[i]$ in a descending order for each step. Note, that we start to compare from the last bit position in a descending order. For example, in the binary string 100 which represents the number 4 with bit-length 3, we start iterating from the last bit element, that is the bit 1. Moreover, we store the position j in the work tapes and this value has at most logarithmic space. In addition, we also store the position i in the work tapes which contains at most logarithmic space in its binary representation. If it would be the case that $A[i]$ is greater than x , then we reject. We continue the iteration with the next value i while the property that x is the maximum number in the array remains as true. However, we only accept when the value of the variable *answer* is “yes” when initially has the value of “no” by default. The value will be “yes” in the variable *answer* after the whole iteration for each element in the array if and only if there is at least one element $A[i]$ that is equal to x . Furthermore, if the iteration is completed until the last item, then x is greater than or equal to every element in the array A . To sum up, we show we can decide whether x is the maximum of the array A in logarithmic space and thus, $LOG\text{-}MAXIMUM \in L$. \square

THEOREM 5.5. $L \not\subseteq POLYLOGTIME$.

PROOF. The single existence of a problem in L that is not in $POLYLOGTIME$ is sufficient to show $L \not\subseteq POLYLOGTIME$. Hence, this is a consequence of Theorems 5.3 and 5.4. \square

5.2 L versus $\oplus L$

Definition 5.6. XOR-3SAT

INSTANCE: A Boolean formula F that is the conjunctions of a set C of clauses c_1, \dots, c_m , where each c_i consists of the EXCLUSIVE OR (denoted \oplus) of three literals.

QUESTION: Is it the case that F is satisfiable?

REMARKS: $XOR\text{-}3SAT$ is complete for $\oplus L$ [1].

Definition 5.7. MONOTONE-XOR-4SAT

INSTANCE: A Boolean formula F that is the conjunctions of a set C of clauses c_1, \dots, c_m , where each c_i consists of the EXCLUSIVE OR (denoted \oplus) of four positive literals.

QUESTION: Is it the case that F is satisfiable?

REMARKS: $MONOTONE\text{-}XOR\text{-}4SAT \in \oplus L$ because $XOR\text{-}SAT \in \oplus L$ [1].

Algorithm 3 LOG-MAXIMUM's Logarithmic space algorithm

```
1: procedure LOG-MAXIMUM( $n, x, A$ )
2:   /*Compare the bit-length of  $x$  with  $\lceil \log n \rceil$ */
3:   if  $|x| \neq \lceil \log n \rceil$  then
4:     /*Reject*/
5:     return "no"
6:   end if
7:   /*Initialize the variable  $answer$ */
8:    $answer \leftarrow$  "no"
9:   /*Iterate for each element of the array*/
10:  for  $i \leftarrow 1$  to  $n$  do
11:    /*When the element  $A[i]$  bit-length is different of  $\lceil \log n \rceil$ */
12:    if  $|A[i]| \neq \lceil \log n \rceil$  then
13:      /*Reject*/
14:      return "no"
15:    end if
16:    /*Assign the index to the last bit element*/
17:     $j \leftarrow |x|$ 
18:    /*While there are bits to compare*/
19:    while  $j \geq 1$  do
20:      /*Compare the bit in the position  $j$  of  $x$  with the bit in the position  $j$  of  $A[i]$ */
21:      if  $x[j] < A[i][j]$  then
22:        /*Reject because  $A[i]$  is greater than  $x$ */
23:        return "no"
24:        /*Compare the bit in the position  $j$  of  $x$  with the bit in the position  $j$  of  $A[i]$ */
25:      else if  $x[j] > A[i][j]$  then
26:        /*Continue to the next iteration on  $i$ */
27:        break
28:      else
29:        /*Decrement the bit position  $j$  of  $x$  and  $A[i]$ */
30:         $j \leftarrow j - 1$ 
31:      end if
32:    end while
33:    /*After iterating from all the bits of  $x$  and  $A[i]$ */
34:    if  $j = 0$  then
35:      /* $x$  is equal to  $A[i]$ */
36:       $answer \leftarrow$  "yes"
37:    end if
38:  end for
39:  /*Accept if  $answer =$  "yes" and reject when  $answer =$  "no"*/
40:  return  $answer$ 
41: end procedure
```

A logarithmic space transducer is a Turing machine with a read-only input tape, a write-only output tape, and some read/write work tapes [7]. The work tapes must contain at most $O(\log n)$ symbols [7]. A logarithmic space transducer M computes a function $f : \Sigma^* \rightarrow \Sigma^*$, where $f(w)$ is the string remaining on the output tape after M halts when it is started with w on its input tape

[7]. We call f a logarithmic space computable function [7]. We say that a language $L_1 \subseteq \{0, 1\}^*$ is logarithmic space reducible to a language $L_2 \subseteq \{0, 1\}^*$, written $L_1 \leq_l L_2$, if there exists a logarithmic space computable function $f : \{0, 1\}^* \rightarrow \{0, 1\}^*$ such that for all $x \in \{0, 1\}^*$,

$$x \in L_1 \text{ if and only if } f(x) \in L_2.$$

THEOREM 5.8. $XOR\text{-}3SAT \leq_l MONOTONE\text{-}XOR\text{-}4SAT$.

PROOF. We assume that each variable in the Boolean formula F of n variables in $XOR\text{-}3SAT$ is a unique positive integer between 1 and n . We denote as X the set of variables in F from $XOR\text{-}3SAT$. The negative literals are represented as the negative value of each variable value, such that the negative literal of the variable a is $-a$. Since we need to create the positive literals in the language $MONOTONE\text{-}XOR\text{-}4SAT$, then we use the function h such that

$$h(x) = \text{if } (x > 0) \text{ return } (2 \times x) \text{ else return } (-2 \times x + 1).$$

The polynomial time reduction is described in the pseudo code Algorithm 4.

Algorithm 4 Logarithmic space reduction from $XOR\text{-}3SAT$ to $MONOTONE\text{-}XOR\text{-}4SAT$

```

1: /*A set of clauses  $C$  and the set of variables  $X$  of an instance in  $XOR\text{-}3SAT$ */
2: procedure REDUCTION( $C, X$ )
3:   output  $(x \oplus y \oplus y \oplus y)$ 
4:   output  $(z \oplus y \oplus y \oplus y)$ 
5:   /*Iterate for each variable in  $X$ */
6:   for all  $a \in X$  do
7:     output  $(z \oplus x \oplus h(a) \oplus h(-a))$ 
8:   end for
9:   /*Iterate from the clauses of  $C$ */
10:  for all  $(a \oplus b \oplus c) \in C$  do
11:    output  $(z \oplus h(a) \oplus h(b) \oplus h(c))$ 
12:  end for
13: end procedure

```

Note, in this reduction we guarantee that every literal is positive through the function h . In addition, we add new three positive literals x , y and z represented by the positive integers $(2 \times n + 2)$, $(2 \times n + 3)$ and $(2 \times n + 4)$ respectively, where n is the cardinality in the set of variables X . If every clause $(a \oplus b \oplus c) \in C$ can be converted to $(h(a) \oplus h(b) \oplus h(c))$, then we obtain a new Boolean formula where every literal is positive. However, this does not guarantee that for every variable a , the literals $h(a)$ and $h(-a)$ have opposite values. This is guaranteed with the new variables x and y , such that we consider the clauses $(x \oplus y \oplus y \oplus y)$, $(y \oplus y \oplus y)$ and $(x \oplus h(a) \oplus h(-a))$. The reason is because the value $x = 0$ is obligated with the clauses $(x \oplus y \oplus y \oplus y)$ and $(y \oplus y \oplus y)$ and the evaluated clauses $(0 \oplus h(a) \oplus h(-a))$ guarantee the opposite values of the literals $h(a)$ and $h(-a)$. Finally, we add the new variable z for every modified clause which has three positive literals. In this way, if we have a satisfying truth assignment of the new Boolean formula in $MONOTONE\text{-}XOR\text{-}4SAT$ where $z = 0$, then F will be satisfiable under the same truth assignment just excluding the literals x , y and z and replacing the value of the positive literal $h(a)$ by the value of a that can be a positive or negative literal. In addition, if the new Boolean formula in $MONOTONE\text{-}XOR\text{-}4SAT$ has a satisfying truth assignment where $z = 1$, then we can create a new satisfying truth assignment where $z = 0$ just replacing each evaluation of $h(a) = 1$ by $h(a) = 0$ and $h(b) = 0$ by $h(b) = 1$ and including the same procedure for the variables x and y where a and b are literals of F . In general, the whole algorithm

uses logarithmic space in the work tapes since the new Boolean formula is created in the output tape into a write-only way. Consequently, we obtain $XOR-3SAT \leq_l MONOTONE-XOR-4SAT$. \square

THEOREM 5.9. *MONOTONE-XOR-4SAT is complete for $\oplus L$.*

PROOF. Since the language $XOR-3SAT$ can be reduced to $MONOTONE-XOR-4SAT$ in logarithmic space, then $MONOTONE-XOR-4SAT$ is hard for $\oplus L$. Furthermore, $MONOTONE-XOR-4SAT$ is in $\oplus L$. To sum up, we obtain $MONOTONE-XOR-4SAT$ is complete for $\oplus L$. \square

Definition 5.10. CLIQUE-COVER-2

INSTANCE: An undirected graph $G = (V, E)$.

QUESTION: Is it the case that V can be covered by two cliques?

REMARKS: $CLIQUE-COVER-2 \in L$ [2], [6].

THEOREM 5.11. *MONOTONE-XOR-4SAT \leq_l CLIQUE-COVER-2.*

PROOF. We assume that each positive literal in the Boolean formula F of n variables is a unique positive integer between 1 and n . Consequently, for two literals a and b we consider the vertex $v_{a,b}$. In order to do not repeat the vertices $v_{a,b}$ and $v_{b,a}$ which represent the same tuple, then we create the function f such that for every tuple (a, b) of natural numbers

$$f((a, b)) = \text{if } (a \leq b) \text{ return } v_{a,b} \text{ else return } v_{b,a}.$$

Moreover, for each clause $c_i = (a \oplus b \oplus c \oplus d)$ in F where a, b, c and d are positive literals represented by natural numbers, we create the function g such that

$$g(c_i) = \{(a, b), (c, d), ((a, c), (b, d)), ((a, d), (b, c))\}$$

where for every pair $((x, y), (p, q))$ we have the *key* = (x, y) and the *value* = (p, q) . We also assume that every instance of $CLIQUE-COVER-2$ can be represented by a collection of tuples (v, w) such that v and w are vertices and (v, w) is an edge of the graph instance $G = (V, E)$. Note, that we use the word “**collection**” and not set, because there might exist repeated edges in any instance of $CLIQUE-COVER-2$ from this representation even though E is a set. The polynomial time reduction is described in the pseudo code Algorithm 5.

Algorithm 5 Logarithmic space reduction from $MONOTONE-XOR-4SAT$ to $CLIQUE-COVER-2$

- 1: /*A set of clauses C of an instance in $MONOTONE-XOR-4SAT$ */
 - 2: **procedure** REDUCTION(C)
 - 3: COMPLETE-GRAPH(C)
 - 4: SEPARATION(C)
 - 5: **end procedure**
-

Initially, we create a complete graph constructed with the vertices $f((a, b))$ such that there exists a clause c_i in F that contains the positive literals a and b . This creation is made in the Algorithm 6. In that procedure, we avoid to create some edge (v, v) with a single vertex v . For that reason, we make the comparisons $f(key_1) \neq f(key_2)$, $f(key_1) \neq f(value_2)$, $f(value_1) \neq f(key_2)$ and $f(value_1) \neq f(value_2)$ before to add any edge. After the execution of this procedure, we can create in many ways two cliques which cover the vertices of the created graph.

In the second step, we start to add pair of vertices which are not connected into the created graph. This modification is made in the Algorithm 7. This guarantee that for every used positive integer $i > 0$ in the Algorithm 7, the vertices v_i and w_i are not connected. Moreover, the vertex v_i is not connected to the vertex $f(key_1)$ while the vertex w_i is not connected to the vertex $f(value_1)$

Algorithm 6 Logarithmic space algorithm of the generation of a complete graph

```
1: /*A set of clauses  $C$  of an instance in  $MONOTONE-XOR-4SAT^*$ */
2: procedure COMPLETE-GRAPH( $C$ )
3:   /*Iterate from the clauses of  $C^*$ */
4:   for all  $c_1 \in C$  do
5:     for all  $c_2 \in C$  do
6:       for all  $(key_1, value_1) \in g(c_1)$  do
7:         for all  $(key_2, value_2) \in g(c_2)$  do
8:           if  $f(key_1) \neq f(key_2)$  then
9:             output  $(f(key_1), f(key_2))$ 
10:          end if
11:          if  $f(key_1) \neq f(value_2)$  then
12:            output  $(f(key_1), f(value_2))$ 
13:          end if
14:          if  $f(value_1) \neq f(key_2)$  then
15:            output  $(f(value_1), f(key_2))$ 
16:          end if
17:          if  $f(value_1) \neq f(value_2)$  then
18:            output  $(f(value_1), f(value_2))$ 
19:          end if
20:        end for
21:      end for
22:    end for
23:  end for
24: end procedure
```

where the tuples key_1 and $value_1$ contains exactly the literals of the clause $c_1 \in C$. However, the vertices v_i and w_i are connected to every other vertex in the modified graph including the previous pair of disconnected vertices v_j and w_j for every positive integer $0 < j < i$.

In this way, we guarantee if the vertices of the modified graph can be covered by two cliques, then one clique contains v_i and the another one contains w_i for every used positive integer $i > 0$ in the Algorithm 7. However, if v_i and w_i are in different cliques, then the vertices $f(key_1)$ and $f(value_1)$ are in different cliques as well, where the tuples $(key_1, value_1)$ are in the set $g(c_1)$ for each clause $c_1 \in C$. This means for every pair $(key_1, value_1)$ in the set $g(c_1)$ of each clause $c_1 \in C$, if the vertices of the modified graph can be covered by two cliques, then one clique contains the vertex $f(key_1)$ and the another one contains the vertex $f(value_1)$.

Is it the case of F is satisfiable when the vertices in the final modified graph can be covered by two cliques? Yes, think in the properties of the tuples $(key_1, value_1)$ in the set $g(c_1)$ of each clause $c_1 \in C$. Each pair is a simple formula in which one of the two tuples should be true and the other false where every tuple represents a clause. The key observation is that every pair in the set $\{((a, b), (c, d)), ((a, c), (b, d)), ((a, d), (b, c))\}$ of each clause $(a \oplus b \oplus c \oplus d) \in C$ satisfies that exactly one of the clauses

- (1) $(a \oplus b)$ or $(c \oplus d)$ in the pair $((a, b), (c, d))$ should be true and the other false and,
- (2) $(a \oplus c)$ or $(b \oplus d)$ in the pair $((a, c), (b, d))$ should be true and the other false and,
- (3) $(a \oplus d)$ or $(b \oplus c)$ in the pair $((a, d), (b, c))$ should be true and the other false

Algorithm 7 Logarithmic space algorithm from a possible valid separation into two cliques

```
1: /*A set of clauses  $C$  of an instance in MONOTONE-XOR-4SAT*/
2: procedure SEPARATION( $C$ )
3:   /*Assign the variable  $i$  to 0*/
4:    $i \leftarrow 0$ 
5:   /*Iterate from the clauses of  $C$ */
6:   for all  $c_1 \in C$  do
7:     for all  $(key_1, value_1) \in g(c_1)$  do
8:        $i \leftarrow i + 1$ 
9:       for all  $c_2 \in C$  do
10:        for all  $(key_2, value_2) \in g(c_2)$  do
11:          if  $f(key_1) \neq f(key_2)$  then
12:            output  $(v_i, f(key_2))$ 
13:          end if
14:          if  $f(key_1) \neq f(value_2)$  then
15:            output  $(v_i, f(value_2))$ 
16:          end if
17:          if  $f(value_1) \neq f(key_2)$  then
18:            output  $(w_i, f(key_2))$ 
19:          end if
20:          if  $f(value_1) \neq f(value_2)$  then
21:            output  $(w_i, f(value_2))$ 
22:          end if
23:        end for
24:      end for
25:      for  $j \leftarrow 1$  to  $i - 1$  do
26:        output  $(v_i, v_j)$ 
27:        output  $(v_i, w_j)$ 
28:        output  $(w_i, v_j)$ 
29:        output  $(w_i, w_j)$ 
30:      end for
31:    end for
32:  end for
33: end procedure
```

if and only if the clause $(a \oplus b \oplus c \oplus d)$ is satisfiable for some truth assignment. Finally, if we assign the variables represented by the vertices in one of the cliques to true and the other variables represented by the another clique to false, then we indeed obtain a satisfying truth assignment for F . Hence, if the vertices in the final modified graph can be covered by two cliques, then F is satisfiable, and this property of the graph is necessary to prove that the Boolean formula F can be satisfiable. Indeed, when the vertices in the final modified graph cannot be covered by two cliques, then this would mean we cannot separate each tuple of every pair $(key_1, value_1)$ by exactly one evaluated as true and the other as false which is equivalent to assume that F is unsatisfiable.

Is this a logarithmic space reduction? Yes, since we can iterate for each clause $c_1 \in C$ with a positive integer n represented in binary string which means the position of the clause in the input from left to right. If it is the first one from left to right then $n = 1$ and if it is the second one then $n = 2$ and so forth... The same thing we can do for the second iteration for each clause $c_2 \in C$ with

another positive integer m represented in binary string. In addition, the iteration for the pairs of tuples of $g(c_1)$ and $g(c_2)$ can be done by two binary integers between 1 and 3 that represents which pair corresponds in the sets $g(c_1)$ and $g(c_2)$. Furthermore, the positive integers i and j are feasible polynomially bounded by the total amount of tuples. Nevertheless, we represent the numbers i and j by two binary strings. Since the binary representation of n, m, i, j and the two numbers between 1 and 3 is logarithmic in relation to the size of the input, then the whole Algorithms 6 and 7 can be run in logarithmic space. On the other hand, we can compose this reduction by another logarithmic space algorithm which converts the collection of edges inside of the output tape into a set of edges, because the logarithmic space reduction is closed under composition [5]. However, our premise states this is not actually necessary for an instance of *CLIQUE-COVER-2*. Hence, the Algorithm 5 is a logarithmic space reduction from *MONOTONE-XOR-4SAT* to *CLIQUE-COVER-2* such that

$$F \in \text{MONOTONE-XOR-4SAT} \text{ if and only if } G \in \text{CLIQUE-COVER-2}$$

and thus, the proof is completed. □

THEOREM 5.12. $L = \oplus L$.

PROOF. The single existence of a complete problem in $\oplus L$ that could be logarithmic space reduced to a problem in L is sufficient to show $L = \oplus L$. Hence, this is a consequence of Theorems 5.9 and 5.11. □

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